

EFFECTS OF VIDEAGOGY ON MATHEMATICS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG GRADE 9 STUDENTS UNDER MODULAR APPROACH

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Abstract

Mathematics teachers are constantly confronted with huge challenges in enhancing teaching and learning processes. With the advent of technology, several educational theorists are advocating ICT – assisted instruction to support, enhance and enable subject matter delivery. In the height of unprecedented global health crisis, the struggle of educational sector to address the learning continuity in the new normal had become the foreground. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of using contextualized learning videos also known as Videagogy or the teaching pedagogy using videos as intervention to the Modular learning approach of grade 9 Mathematics. This research conducted quasi - experiment using pre – test – post – test design. Non-Random Sampling was employed to come up with a sample population of sixty (60) grade 9 respondents from Cabanglasan National High School. The sample was divided into two groups; thirty (30) of them were in the Control Group and thirty (30) were in the Experimental Group. The instrument used in this research was standardized Academic Test. Based from the result of the post-test, which were statistically treated and analyzed using the mean, standard deviation and t – test, the students who were exposed to teacher – made learning videos obtained high mean score and performed significantly better than to the students exposed to non-teacher – made learning videos.

Keywords: Videagogy, Contextualized Learning Videos, Pedagogy, students’ performance, mathematics education

1. INTRODUCTION

In teaching and learning process, teachers play important role in classroom situation and in the accountability of the holistic development of the learners. However, they are recently challenged on the abrupt shift of the Educational System brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic that had sprouted in 2019 up to the present. As a result, many businesses had to close resulting to growing number of non-employments, and poverty rate dramatically inclined, thus Education had to face the challenges of time since Face – to – Face Classes was strictly prohibited. In some other countries, Online Classes were utilized considering that they belong to highly advanced in terms of technology adaptation. However, country such as ours could never totally go in parallel with other countries because only 70.7 percent of the population in

Philippines is using internet in 2019 survey (Sanchez, 2020). Fifty – five (55) percent of Filipino students have access to internet and only twenty – six (26) percent are from public schools (Kritz, 2020).

DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones, reiterated in her speeches that Education must continue. The Learning Continuity Plan of the DepEd conceived the idea to have Blended Learning as part of the solution to normalize the activities in Education, that is using two or more approaches that may fit to the needs of every learner as to its demographic profile, availability of educational technologies and accessibility to Internet Connectivity.

Cabanglasan National High School in particular, adapted a learning delivery mode combining the Modules and TV-Radio-Based Instruction set by the Department of Education. However, majority of the school population could not have full access to the latter mode resulting them to utilize only the Printed Learning Modules. These said printed instructional materials were provided by the Department of Education to the learners through classroom-based distribution and retrieval per quarter of the Academic Year alongside with the Weekly Home Learning Plan to be given to each student as their Learning Guide. Self-learning modules include adaptable exercises that can be done by students of varying skill levels.

Based on the First Quarter of the Distribution/Retrieval of the Printed Modules, the teacher – researcher had recorded myriad of issues among students such as copying of answers from the answer key, loss of interest towards their studies, Poor retention of prior knowledge, and poor performance in answering the teacher-made tests. Several Factors affecting students’ behaviors which include socio – economic status, demographic profile especially those areas affected by arm conflict, early marriage and teenage pregnancy, lack of parental interventions and poor access to technological trends were the observations of the researcher in her Home Visits.

The first quarter grades of the students implied that there were students identified as at-risk of failing thus, learning interventions must be given to them to cope with the struggling academic performance. One intervention that the researcher had implemented was giving of contextualized Learning Videos to the students. Jonas & Bradley (2013) coined the term “Videagogy”, pronounced as vid-e-ah-go-jee that means using short videos as new teaching technique. In the videos, instructions were simplified and less – mastered competencies were emphasized.

As been said, teachers had been striving looking for suitable techniques that ensures quality learning. To augment the curriculum means to search for as many different avenues as possible to make the most important content understandable and learning videos can be of great tool to assist students in gaining deeper understanding of content in Mathematics 9. Furthermore, these videos are contextually made by the teacher having mindful of the clear objectives articulated beforehand and the step-by-step procedure on a specific mathematical skill that the students need to acquire. With the help of Virtual Board App, lessons were pre-recorded, and it can remove barriers to learning in a variety of ways, including but not limited to time freedom for processing information, accommodating students' own pace, and promoting positive teacher-student relationships with personalized videos (Vierstra, 2014).

According to the Educator’s Diary published in 1995, “teaching takes place only when learning does.” It is measured through students’ performances therefore; they need teachers who could guide the instruction in the modules to ensure that quality education must not be forgotten even in this unprecedented time due to global pandemic.

It is well established that fundamental numeric skills continue to be essential for the cognitive development of students. Moreover, they give the necessary foundation for the higher mathematics required for success in the industry and currently included in a basic education (Ball *et al.*, as cited in Cannon, 2017). Thus, the researcher viewed this as one of the factors that greatly affect their learning achievement in Mathematics and their interest towards the subject.

Learning Videos as an Instructional Material in Mathematics

The concept of learning videos as a teaching intervention goes beyond technological integration and represents a new trend adaptation for "Net" generations. In the 1980s, educational videos and social media were introduced, resulting in a rapid transformation of educational institutions brought about by educational technology (Ali, 2019). The combination of the use of videos as pedagogy in teaching was termed "videagogy" by Jonas & Bradley (2013) and it can be beneficial to teaching and learning. It supports various pedagogical strategies that provides opportunity for the students to be independent learners.

Videos created for the purpose of education might serve as supplemental reading or lectures. Content, lecture, short knowledge snippets, tutorials, and the like fall under this category (Carmichael, n.d). Students are demonstrating an increased desire to take initiative in their education by cultivating a personalized learning environment both inside and outside of the classroom (Rasi and Polkela, 2016). Learners can increase their learning results by watching videos on their cell phones, which are effective instruments that instruct students on proper skills. Additionally, it may result in a noticeably increased degree of learning motivation, self-assurance in the process of acquiring a skill, and overall contentment with the course (Lee *et al.*, 2016).

Tan and Pearce (2011) indicated that the use of video in education was an effective way to engage students and support their understanding. Brame (2016) claims that using video in the classroom would help teachers convey key ideas to students and increase their interest in learning. Here are several ways in which videos can aid in learning and development, including the acquisition of new abilities, the modification of existing perspectives, the stimulation of cognitive processes, and the storage of previously acquired knowledge (Taslibeyaz *et al.*, 2017). Likewise, the use of video-based learning improves instructional methodologies and learning outcomes (Yousef *et al.*, 2014) and improve access to real-world examples (Carmichael, n.d.). Students can learn from the video's in-depth examples and replay it as many times as they need to fully understand (Ramlogan *et al.*, 2014).

Advances in video recording and distribution are helping make "ubiquitous learning" possible; this is the process of gaining knowledge regardless of time or place. It's a low-cost, convenient way to get an education that doesn't limit students to a classroom setting, and it allows for individual learners based on each need. Students are said to obtain these practical benefits from having their lessons delivered via video (Taslibeyaz *et al.*, 2017)

Related research on problem-based learning discovered that people have a general preference for video over text (Rasi and Polkela, 2016), and eventually, it had indicated that learners appear to appreciate and regard it favorably, liking the independence it allows (Kay and Kletskin, 2012). In addition, current research indicates that the introduction of video into a course structure can affect students' motivation to engage with the learning resources.

Accordingly, students prefer shorter video to lengthier ones (Carmichael, n.d.) because they are more easily digestible (Doolittle *et al.*, 2015). Videos improve learning and encourage

students to utilize them again (Giannakos *et al.*, 2016). The concern regarding the preference for shorter video suggested that learning videos may be delivered in chunks to overcome the difficulties of digesting images and integrating them with past knowledge as new information is presented. Segmentation enables students to pause and study content at their own pace, hence reducing cognitive load.

Cruse (n.d.) cited a conclusion that people will generally remember 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see while 50% of what they hear and see. In addition, in the recent study of Islam, (2020,) he found out that pre-recorded video lectures are preferred than live lectures due to their flexibility, convenience, and educational effectiveness. Thus, this learning platform is richly beneficial to learners of 21st Century.

In addition, the authenticity of the videos might foster a sense of belonging in the digital classroom (Vierstra, 2014). Accordingly, with video, written directions are easier to understand, it makes lessons more Universal Design for Learning (UDL) – Friendly, it makes distance learning more equitable, it builds relationships with personalized videos and it provides accommodations during distance learning.

Teachers of Mathematics are greatly challenged on how to bridge the learning gap and how to sustain learning that enable students become equipped with essential mathematical skills needed. Teachers today have a wider range of resources at their disposal to aid students in grasping mathematical concepts, and a blend of conventional and contemporary pedagogical approaches can effectively serve learners of varying abilities (Capuno *et al.*, 2019) especially that the subject itself is very challenging. Thus, the most suitable tool that the researcher believes to be of great help to the teachers and learners of Mathematics is to incorporate authentic well – structured learning videos to the delivery of the lessons.

Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics

Filipino kids performed poorly on the International Assessment of Mathematics and Science compared to pupils from other nations, according to the 2019 edition of the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS).

According to Abaidoo (2018), the academic achievement of students influences the success or failure of academic institutions. They added that academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by teacher over a specific period of time. Moreover, Academic performance of students has a direct impact on the overall goals of life.

Tety (2016), on the other hand, emphasized that instructional materials effect academic success. In addition, he discovered that learners in Nigeria who are taught with instructional materials perform better than those who are not. With that, the use of instructional materials would allow the students to understand the concept of a subject better and they perform better than student taught without instructional materials (Adalikwu, 2013).

Theoretical supports of learning videos

Learning Videos are considered to be indispensable learning resource material that the teachers of today's generation could practically use. This teaching – learning intervention could be supported with the educational theories namely; The Cognitive Theory of multimedia learning, and Constructivism Theories.

The "cognitive theory of multimedia learning" (Mayer 2014, Clark and Mayer, 2016) is a crucial foundation for comprehending the processes that determine whether learning through video is beneficial or detrimental. He further discussed that the cognitive theory of multimedia learning is founded on the learning principles that have been established by cognitive science: The human information processing system has dual channels for processing both visual and graphical information as well as auditory and verbal information. Multimedia instructional messages should assist the right cognitive processing of the learner without overwhelming their mental resources. So, when making videos of lessons, it is strongly suggested that they be broken into segments that are easy to understand. The Multimedia Learning Theory says that well-structured video courses can help students think about how they think, and that students can understand the lessons in the videos while they are learning.

The role of educators in this instructional support is to adhere to the ideas of the theory and processes discussed in designing and creating the videos and in choosing the activities and educational information.

Action Research Questions

Generally, the study investigated the effects of videagogy or the pedagogy of teaching using learning videos specifically the contextualized learning videos towards the mathematics academic performance among grade 9 students under modular approach.

Specifically, this study had sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' performance as exposed to the contextualized learning videos and those of non-contextualized learning videos in terms of Pretest and Posttest?
2. Is there a significant difference on the students' performance in relation to pretest and posttest as exposed to the contextualized learning videos and those of non-contextualized learning videos?

Hypothesis

Given here, is the hypothesis of the study:

There is no significant difference on the students' performance in relation to pretest and posttest as exposed to the contextualized learning videos and those of non-contextualized learning videos.

2. METHODS

The purpose of this study is to examine the effects of "Videagogy" on the academic performance of grade 9 mathematics students under modular approach. During the first quarter, it was observed that students using the modular approach without any interventions struggled to comprehend mathematical concepts, causing others to copy the answers from the answer key, leaving their answer sheets blank, or notifying the teacher for their inability to grasp the concept.

The researcher incorporated technology in the use of contextualized learning videos as teaching pedagogy that served as intervention that could potentially help students who have access to cell phones, netbooks, laptops, and other devices with the capacity to store pre-recorded video

memories of the instructional lessons requiring only a minimal need for an internet connection, as opposed to the laborious and time-consuming Home Visit.

Contextualized learning videos are quick tutorials and were made as intervention or supplemental learning tool along with the modular approach of learning. The teacher created short learning videos, chunking lessons into parts so that it could be more accessible for learners in terms of its storing and utilization methods. The students in the experimental group had been exposed to the intervention, while those in the control group had given the option to use any variety of online resources, including videos created by other relevant experts, as their supplementary learning tool.

The contextualized learning videos included a brief introduction to the topic, its objectives, and the target competency, followed by a presentation of the mathematical ideas to be taught and a series of examples, as well as their application to real-world problems.

For the medium of instruction of the learning videos, the teacher used mixed languages such as English and Bisaya.

A specified group chat and Facebook group were created respectively for the experimental group with a regular monitoring on their accessibility to the intervention.

Research Design

The researcher employed a Quasi-Experimental Research Design given that the sample under investigation consisted of two groups: Control and Experimental.

The experimental group was provided with pre-recorded, teacher-made learning videos to supplement self-learning modules, whereas the control group was given freedom to select their own non-teacher-created learning videos from various internet platforms or websites.

Participants of the Study

Research participants were grade nine (9) learners of Cabanglasan National High School, Cabanglasan, Bukidnon wherein the researcher is teaching mathematics 9 subject. Out of 323 population of the grade 9, Sixty (60) of which were selected using the non-probability sampling procedure. For the purpose of this study, the teacher purposively identified learners who have mobile phones who were then exposed to the intervention. While learners from one intact section were used as the control group of the study or those learners who were exposed to the teacher-made learning videos (TLV).

Before students were explicitly included in the study, parental permission was sought.

Research Instruments

This study utilized standardized academic tests in Mathematics in collecting data on students' academic performance. These are the pretest and posttest, being incorporated in the Teaching and learning materials provided by the Department of Education to the teachers.

The researcher also made the use of self-made learning videos as intervention learning tool for the students under modular approach.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The academic tests used in this study were standardized tests that already underwent quality assurance with respect to content validity and reliability by the curriculum experts of the Department of Education. On the other hand, the teacher-made or contextualized learning videos were validated by two relevant experts such as the two (2) master teachers of the school where the researcher is teaching. A panel of relevant experts could establish the validity of the instruments by exploring theoretical constructs (Bolarinwa, 2016). Inter-rater Reliability Test was done to measure the agreement between ratings of two relevant raters. Specifically, it used Cohen's Kappa statistics. With acceptable Kappa coefficient of 0.89, the research instrument is therefore reliable.

Data Collection Methods

After obtaining approval from the district supervisor and the school principal, and after securing consent from the parents of the participants, the teacher-researcher started conducting the research in the first half of quarter three of the school year; 2020 – 2021. A 30-item pre-assessment or diagnostic test was administered to the learners and utilized as a baseline for a substantial change in learning after the learning intervention will be implemented. To facilitate the experimental group's access to the teacher-made learning videos, a private Facebook and Messenger group was established. On the other hand, learners from Control Group were given with self-learning modules only following the distribution and retrieval phases set by the Department of Education, giving them freedom to choose nonteacher-made learning videos or any learning video materials available online. The teacher-researcher conducted an orientation or a conference to follow-up and ensure that Control Group used non-teacher-made learning videos as intervention to their modular learning. After the strategy had implemented, a 30 - item achievement test or post – test was administered.

The results of the pretest and the posttest were collected, coded, tallied and analyzed in determining the effects of using the contextualized learning videos on students' academic performance.

Data Analysis Plan

This study used mean, percentage and standard deviation to answer problem 1. Paired-sample t-test was used in determining if there is a significant difference of the mean scores in relation to the pretest and posttest of both groups or in answering problem 2 of this study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the Lavene Test results generated from the pretests scores, the two group samples came from a class with homogeneous variance data. This is a good indication that the respondents included in the study are almost of the same level of learning abilities thus, providing a good baseline for the experimentation process.

Table 3.1. Lavene Test Result Details on the Pretest Scores of the Two Group of Respondents

RESULTS DETAILS				
SOURCE	SS	Df	MS	
Between Treatments	14.867	1	14.867	F = 3.87805
Within Treatments	222.3496	58	3.8336	
Total	237.2166	59		

p-value=0.53704

Correlation is not significant at 0.05 level

The f – ratio value is 3.87805 and the p-value is .053704. The result is not significant at $p < .05$. Thus, the requirement of homogeneity of the sample is met.

Table 3.2. Student’s Pretest Mean Scores between two groups

PRETEST RESULTS			
GROUPS	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Non-contextualized Learning Videos	30	11.13	2.98
Contextualized Learning Videos	30	13.27	3.87

Table 3.2 presents the Student’s Pretest Mean Scores between two groups. As shown, the mean scores of the non-teacher – made learning videos is 11.13 while for those exposed to the teacher learning videos is 13.27 which a slight difference existed between two groups. This supports to explain that the students’ level of cognition is almost the same which is a good demarcation if there is an effect in terms of their academic performances after exposure to the learning interventions employed. This would also show the difference of their standard deviations in which both data is not totally scattered from the mean scores. The same observations were evidently noted by Ali (2019) and Mendoza (2015) on their studies Impacts of Watching Videos on Academic Performance at University Level and Effectiveness of Video Presentation to Students Learning that student’s performance before employing the intervention were relatively lower than their performance after instructional videos had been employed.

Table 3.3. Student’s Posttest Mean Scores between two groups

POST - TEST RESULTS			
GROUPS	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Non-Contextualized Learning Videos	30	13.17	3.21
Contextualized Learning Videos	30	18.07	2.80

Table 3.3 presents the Student’s Posttest Mean Scores between two groups. As gleaned from table 3, those students exposed to the teacher-made learning videos indicate a mean score of 18.07 which show high mean scores than those with non-teacher – made learning videos. This can be explained that exposure to the educational technology authentically made by the teacher within the subject in Mathematics is better than those in the non-teacher – made learning videos available online. This research findings are consistent with the results of the studies of Lalian (2018) on the effects of video media in mathematics learning on students’

cognitive and affective aspects and of Robertson (2020) on his study about determining the impacts of lecture videos on student outcomes that whenever classes are integrated with technology students academically perform better. To quote, Lalian (2018) averred that the use of videos as a learning media in mathematics plays a role in improving students' motivation in learning, enhancing students' knowledge and understanding of the lesson and improving the students' achievements.

Table 3.4 Level of Significant Differences on the Students' Performance Between the Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores

GROUPS		N	Mean	P – value
Pretest vs. Post-test (df = 29)				
Control	Pre-test	30	11.13	0.02
	Post-test	30	13.17	
Experimental	Pre-test	30	13.27	0.00
	Post-test	30	18.07	

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (two-tailed)

Based on Table 3.4, the results indicate that the two groups are significantly different. The pretest-posttest p value is 0.02 and 0.00, respectively and found significant at 0.05 level. However, the two p-values indicates further that the mean score of the students exposed to contextualized learning videos is significantly higher than that of the mean score of students exposed to non-contextualized learning videos in Mathematics 9 class under Modular Approach.

This finding obtained the same results with the study of Shaheen (2017) on Impact of ICT enriched modular approach on academic achievement of biology students and of Paavizhi (2019) on her study about effectiveness of video assisted learning module that whenever students are exposed to an instructional strategy there is a notable significant difference in terms of their pre-test and post-test in favor of the experimental group. Paavizhi (2019) added that the visual and the audio combination in the videos have helped the users process the information in a natural manner and could further improve their academic performances.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This section draws conclusions, and makes relevant recommendations for the study recommendations.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. The mean scores of the students as exposed to the teacher-made learning videos and those of nonteacher-made learning videos in terms of pre-test are 13.27 and 11.13, respectively while the mean scores of the two groups in terms of post-test are 18.07 and 13.17. Therefore, the students under experimental group obtained higher scores than those students under Control Group.
2. The students exposed to Teacher – made Learning Videos performed significantly better than those students exposed to non-teacher – made learning videos.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested based on the findings of this study.

1. Teachers might try making their own learning videos as remediation to those struggling students and those who are at-risk of failing in Mathematics subject.
2. Teachers especially who are assigned in areas with poor internet connectivity are suggested to try adapting the idea of videagogy since learning videos can just be easily stored in any storage device available and can be watched and replayed. Hence, it is very helpful for the mastery of lesson.
3. A similar action research related to this study might be conducted with respect to the medium of instructional approach involving the use of learning videos with a qualitative data support.

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